

Applications of Metaheuristic Methods in Wireless Telecommunication

Maciej Norberciak

Nokia Technology Center, Strzegomska 36, 53611 Wroclaw, Poland
maciej.noberciak@nokia.com

Abstract. Telecommunications is a cornerstone of our modern society, the market that knows only one rule: constant, rapid expansion. However, to achieve financial viability constant optimizations must be carried out. The aim of this paper is to introduce the reader to metaheuristics as a general-purpose optimization tool and to show some of their successful real-world applications in the wireless telecommunication industry. A metaheuristic-aided antenna design, antenna placement in various networks, a cellular network design and optimization, antenna selection and beamforming problems are offered as examples. The article does not have an ambition of being a complete state of the art review but presents a significant sample of a diverse application domain and lists selected bibliographical references that are easy to access and are written in a comprehensible manner, without going into details on the methods used therein.

Keywords: metaheuristics, telecommunication, antenna design, antenna placement, antenna selection, cell planning, MIMO, beamforming.

1 Metaheuristic methods – overview

Many of real-life tasks can be represented as optimization problems, hence developing efficient optimization methods is an intensively advancing research area. Some of those tasks are considered “hard”. For continuous optimization problems, it means that there is no known algorithm which allows finding a global optimum in a finite number of steps. For discrete optimization, it simply means the problem is NP-hard [1]. Where no optimal solution can be found algorithmically (or can’t be found in reasonable time), heuristics are employed – they *may* provide a “good enough” approximation. Heuristic are specific to the problem they solve – a higher-level procedure that generates, selects, parametrizes or finds a heuristic to the task at hand is called metaheuristic. Metaheuristic methods are general-purpose, not domain-specific and yield good results in problems, where solution space is too large to be fully explored [2].

All the metaheuristics act randomly to a certain degree. This allows them to counteract the effects of combinatorial explosion – rapid growth of the problem’s complexity caused by how the combinatorics of the problem is affected by its input and constraints. The trade-off is that the solution found is not necessarily the global optimum. Apart from few local search techniques (for example tabu search [3], which uses a

memory structure – tabu list – to avoid being stuck in local optimums) most of the metaheuristics are inspired by nature. First major source of inspiration is physics (or chemistry) – examples are gravitational search algorithm (inspired by the Newtonian laws of gravity and motion [4]), river formation dynamics (based on a manner in which water forms a river bed, taking into account soil erosion and sediment deposition [5]), harmony search (inspired by jazz musicians improvising in perfect harmony [6]), or simulated annealing (based on a metallurgical process where metal is heated up and then cooled in a controlled manner [7]). The second source of inspiration is biology, where one can find methods based on our natural evolution – various genetic and evolutionary algorithms (mimicking reproduction, mutation and recombination of genes, and natural selection [8]). Finally, swarm intelligence-based methods take inspiration from swarms or colonies of living organisms, for example ant colony optimization (pheromone-based communication of ants is mimicked [9]), artificial bee colony (simulating an intelligent foraging behavior of a honey bee swarm [10]), or firefly algorithm (inspired by flashing and a sexual attraction mechanism of Lampyridae insects [11]). As metaheuristics emulate nature’s approach to problem solving and learn lessons from it on a more abstract level, they are all treated as a form of artificial intelligence.

2 Metaheuristics in wireless telecommunication – selected applications

2.1 Wireless telecommunication networks

The number of devices connected to the Internet already surpassed the number of humans alive and is rapidly growing. Some forecasts even claim that there will be 125 billion (sic!) connected devices in 2030 [12]. In January 2017, the total population of planet Earth was around 7.5 billion people – half of them were using the Internet, two thirds were using mobile phones [13]. Two years later, the total number of mobile subscriptions is estimated to have exceeded eight billion for the first time, reaching 8.3 billion subscriptions in 2019 [14]. Cisco VN Index reports an 18-fold increase in mobile data traffic between 2011 and 2016 [15]. With “just” 1.1 billion fixed broadband subscriptions worldwide (2018) [16] mobile networks are and for foreseeable future will be the main data transmission vehicles.

Apart from cellular networks humans usually live within the coverage areas of multiple other wireless networks – WiFi, Bluetooth, DECT to name just a few – and are using multiple wireless communication technologies. There are common elements to those networks, and a common set of challenges to overcome. The application domains of those challenges can be roughly divided in four categories: hardware design (with problems like antenna design and placement on the mounting platform), data transmission (e.g. channel and frequency assignment, optimization of spectrum utilization, protocol validation, beamforming) and network design (cell planning, path routing and optimization etc.) [17]. The examples that follow are not exhaustive in present view but try to offer a diverse sample of subject domain.

2.2 Antenna design

Designing an antenna is not an easy task. Just like in many other engineering problems, requirements and constraints are numerous and they interact with one another in a complex manner, and just like in many other engineering problems, concessions and tradeoffs must be made. The challenge of designing an antenna for a spacecraft is even greater, because factors like volume, mass, or power budget became very important. Finally, a delicate instrument must survive heavy Gs during lift-off and a somewhat difficult environment in space. The design process, despite numerous advancements in the field, remains largely manual, strongly relying on the engineer's experience and domain knowledge.

On April 18, 2014, NASA's Lunar Atmosphere and Dust Environment Explorer (LADEE) crashed near the eastern rim of Sundman V crater on the far side of the Moon [18]. An eight-month mission was ended deliberately after the spacecraft run out of fuel needed to maintain its orbit. But the violent manner of LADEE's retirement was not unique – after all, humanity has purposefully struck moon with various devices since Ranger 7 sent first close up images of lunar surface back in 1964 [19]. What was unique was the antenna system that LADEE used to communicate with the Earth.

The use of evolutionary metaheuristics in antenna design and optimization techniques has been investigated since the 1990s, and were triggered, not surprisingly, with a military application – using GA to design radar absorbing coatings [20]. As the field grew, computer speed increased and electromagnetic simulators improved, NASA has started to develop automatic antenna synthesis tools. First evolved antennas (backed up by a “traditionally” designed ones) went through their baptism of fire during Space Technology 5 (ST5) mission [21], showing better performance in every aspect while requiring less work to create [22]. Techniques developed for ST5 were perfected during LADEE design phase [23]. This time no backups were deemed necessary.

Naturally, space industry is not the only one interested in automatization of an antenna design process. Patch antenna is a low-profile device that can be mounted on flat surface. It consists of a planar sheet ("patch") of metal, printed over a surface of PCB (printed circuit board) with a larger sheet of metal (ground plane) on the other side of PCB. The shape can be triangular, circular or of any other geometry, but most antennas are composed of multiple patches in a rectangular array. Thanks to their thin planar profile, ease of fabrication and integration, patch antennas have plethora of applications (for example, they are commonly used in mobile phones). Again, traditional design requires complicated and time-consuming electromagnetic analysis. Metaheuristics have been successfully applied to help with their design, for example in the form of evolutionary algorithms [24], ant colony optimization [25], or invasive weed optimization [26] (inspired from colonizing weeds which attack a field by means of dispersal and occupy opportunity spaces between the crops; weeds grow and reproduce individually and those which take more unused resources grow faster and produce more offspring). Other types of antennas, for example linear or elliptical arrays, are also being designed with the help of metaheuristics, like cuckoo search [27] (based on a parasitic brooding behavior of some cuckoo species) or particle swarm optimization [28] (inspired by social behavior of bird flocking or fish schooling [29]).

2.3 Antenna placement

Advances in computing technology and fabrication techniques are expected to allow site-specific and evolving antennas, that are considering the electromagnetic characteristic of the environment in which the antenna is going to be installed (*in situ*). It was already successful, but as for now there is no reported research in areas other than satellite design [30]. In more “down to Earth” applications, commercially available and off-the-shelf products are typically used, that is, the design is not needed. Still, the problem of antenna placement on a platform (for example, devices, vehicles, masts, buildings) remains. Typically, this is done using engineer’s expertise and judgement, but complex environment and interactions between an antenna and a platform may defy human’s intuition when it comes to choosing an optimal antenna location. Combination of a powerful electromagnetics simulator and a robust optimization algorithm (for example metaheuristics) is needed to automate this task.

Nowadays, almost all vehicles, for example trains, ships, airplanes, or cars, are equipped with antennas, which are ranging from “traditional” AM/FM, through satellite navigation, TV, to mobile network ones. Electromagnetic considerations must go along with the aerodynamic and sometimes even the aesthetic ones. Traditionally, antennas are placed on top of transportation platforms (the roof), but the optimal placement can be counterintuitive. First practical application of metaheuristics for a vehicular antenna placement was a receiving antenna on a train. The transmitter is located along the tracks and the goal is to receive the strongest signal possible. A genetic algorithm has found that the antenna should actually be placed between the roof and the front windows. What is interesting is that all the top locations were discarded early on by the seventh iteration of the algorithm [31].

There is one serious disadvantage to roof-mounted antennas – they protrude from the vehicle. Engineers and designers try to make antennas smaller, so their profile does not affect aerodynamics or aesthetic properties of the vehicle. This challenge may be overcome with glass mounted antennas, built from thin conducting materials and laminated between layers of glass in the vehicle windows. An additional difficulty is to decrease the number of antennas – combine different aperture requirements into one physical antenna system. Finally, effects of wind noise, reflecting, and scattering vary from vehicle to vehicle, forcing the engineers to rely on “gut feelings” and “rules of thumb”, and make multiple experiments to modify antenna configuration. Fortunately, both design and placement of the glass-mounted antenna can be done with the help of metaheuristics. A genetic algorithm has been shown to be an effective tool [32] that helps in creating combined LTE/GPS antennas and mounting them in the windshield.

Most mounting platforms are not designed to move, but that does not make the antenna placement much easier. One of the key concepts in the IoT is ambient intelligence, that is an environment which is sensitive and responsive to the presence of human beings. The environment must be able to determine location of the user to offer context-aware services. Radio frequency identification technology (RFID) is commonly used to achieve this goal in smart buildings – high precision must go hand in hand with low cost (which means a minimum number of antennas). In traditional approach, human must manually scan a card or barcode to mark entering particular area.

Similar problem exists with objects – e.g. packages moving through a distribution center. Automatic tag scanning saves time and labor costs at portals (for example doors or gates). The design objective is to maximize read accuracy as human or object moves through the gate. The accuracy is influenced by many factors, like limited reading range, tag location and orientation, or local interference. As it is infeasible to fix tag position or orientation when it moves through, multiple reader antennas are mounted on the portals. Naturally, the cost (number of antennas) has to be optimized. Even such, one could think, trivial task, as positioning RFID reader antennas at the portals is often too complex for classical optimization algorithms. and metaheuristics (for example genetic algorithms) must be used [33]. Larger-scale problems encompass whole, topologically diverse, floors of buildings. There differential evolution [34], genetic [35] and memetic algorithms [36] have been successfully used to plan sensor and RFID reader networks.

2.4 Cell planning

Solving an antenna placement (sometimes called base station placement or cell planning) problem is one the first steps in the design of mobile telecommunications network. The goal of the latter is to find the best set of antenna locations, maximizing coverage and quality of service, while minimizing the number of antennas. There is a substantial number of variables and constraints that need to be taken into consideration. Antenna parameters (such as position in three dimensional space, elevation, azimuth, and power) have to be determined, taking into account terrain features (for example high buildings, hills, or mountains), infrastructure (site access, electrical and core network connections), electromagnetic pollution, safety regulations and finally the cost (not only the antenna device itself, but also the lease for mast or rooftop space, for example Manhattan has over 1000 buildings with rooftop cell phone antennas, with a monthly fee up to 10000\$ per site [37]). A manual design process is challenging, time-consuming, and error prone. Therefore, automatic aid in form of metaheuristic-based optimization tools quickly attracted the attention of both researchers and mobile network operators. Genetic algorithms have been successfully applied to optimize antenna positioning in 2G [38], 3G [39], and 4G [40] networks. Other methods include particle swarm optimization [41] and a grey wolf optimizer [42] (inspired from a wolves hunting process) which have been used for LTE cell planning.

Cell planning aims at solving multiple problems at the same time: equipment location, spectrum utilization, power allocation, traffic load balancing, and so on. Such multi-objective optimization of a cellular network has been studied since GSM (2G) was introduced, with good results obtained thanks to for example evolutionary [43] or bat algorithms [44] (inspired by the hunting behavior of bats, who search the prey with the help of echolocation, changing pulse emission rate, frequency, and loudness [45]). The real challenge came with 3G, when cellular networks became heterogeneous and optimization had to be done across all Radio Access Technologies (RATs) simultaneously. A wide range of metaheuristics had been tested on theoretical models [46]. Some success was achieved with a simulated annealing-based technique, developed in cooperation between Nokia and Deutsche Telekom [47], but the best results reported come

from another metaheuristic – coral reef optimization [48]. This algorithm is based on the process of coral reefs' formation, simulating different phases of coral reproduction (sexual – external broadcast spawning and internal brooding, and asexual – budding and fragmentation), and fight for space in the reef, which ultimately renders an efficient algorithm for solving large-scale, highly constrained optimization problems. Applying it to optimization of network deployment across all the technologies (2G, 3G and 4G) in Spain lead to a potential reduction of total investment cost in range of 400 million euros, which constituted 15% of base cost [49].

2.5 Antenna selection in MIMO

With rapidly growing volume of data passed through wireless networks, capacity, performance and quality of services have become main design challenges. Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems are one of the ways to address those challenges. In MIMO multiple antennas are deployed on both transmitter and receiver side, providing parallel communication sub-channels. Key performance and capacity characteristics, along with spectral efficiency are enhanced thanks to spatial multiplexing, diversity combining and appropriate space-time coding [50]. The main advantage of a MIMO network over a regular one is that it can multiply the capacity of a wireless connection without requiring more spectrum. MIMO technology is now widespread in commercial use, and it has been standardized for mobile telephony networks since 3G. Unfortunately, the hardware cost of radio-frequency (RF) chains (e.g. amplifiers, digital-analog and analog-digital converters, filters) increases with the number of antenna elements (which are relatively cheap in comparison). One feasible approach to overcome this setback is based on the concept of antenna selection schemes [51], where only a subset of transmit or receive antennas is employed. The basic idea is to choose X 'best' antennas out of Y available antennas, lessening the number of required RF chains from X to Y while keeping most of advantages of the full MIMO system. Antenna selection allows for reduction of hardware complexity of a MIMO system (thus reducing its overall cost) without sacrificing its capacity or performance. For a large number of antennas, optimal subset selection requires an exhaustive search, limiting practical application of algorithmic approaches. A number of metaheuristic techniques were used with good results: genetic [52] (where chromosomes are represented as binary strings), hybrid genetic [53] (where integer values were used in chromosomes) and real-value genetic algorithms (RVGA, where real values were used in representation of candidate solutions) [54] have all been shown to attain nearly the same performance as the optimum, exhaustive search algorithm [55], but with drastically reduced computational complexity. Similar results were obtained with artificial bee colony [56], biogeography [57] (which use mathematical models to describe the allocation and migration of species across various geographical regions [58]) and particle swarm optimization algorithms [59].

2.6 Beamforming problems

During the last few years, a concept of massive multiple-input multiple-output systems has drawn attention of wireless telecommunication community. Massive MIMO is an

extension of MIMO – typical MIMO system employs between 2 and 8 antenna elements, where massive MIMO uses dozens (64, 96 or even 128). In addition to antenna selection problem, beamforming is also a challenge in massive MIMO. In beamforming elements in an antenna array are used in such a way that signals at particular angles experience constructive interference while others experience destructive interference. For a single user it's relatively easy to design a beamforming vector that maximizes signal power, but it's quite difficult to find the balance between maximizing the signal power and minimizing the interference leakage, especially for multiple users [60]. As the problem is generally NP-hard [61], metaheuristic methods seem an obvious choice for potential solution – tabu search [62], genetic algorithms [63], simulated annealing [64] and differential evolution [65] have been used with good results.

But the beamforming is a broader problem – with the increasing number of wireless devices and simultaneous increase in noise and interference, beamforming methods have attracted considerable attention. So called “smart” or adaptive antennas use dynamically adaptive beampatterns, thus reducing interference, improving system capacity and spectrum efficiency. There are several types of optimum statistical beamformers, but in order to make them robust against errors, optimization methods have to be applied. Metaheuristic methods like firefly algorithms [66], particle swarm optimization [67], genetic and gravitational search algorithms have proven useful in this area. Another interesting problem is distributed (or collaborative) beamforming, e.g. in wireless sensor networks, where sensor nodes collaboratively create a virtual antenna array in order to direct their combined radiating power in the intended direction [69]. For such problems good solutions were obtained with help of genetic algorithms [70] and particle swarm-gravitational search hybrid [71].

3 Conclusions

This paper presents a brief summary of wireless telecommunication problems solved with metaheuristic methods. As it can be observed, the challenges in this domain are plenty and very diverse – and they are often computationally intractable with classic exact techniques. The size of telecommunication infrastructure is constantly and rapidly growing – and the underlying optimization problems grow with it. Metaheuristics offer a good alternative to exhaustive methods, as they are able to find a near optimal solutions with acceptable computational effort.

In 1832 Paul Ludwig Schilling von Canstatt has created the first working switched-current electrical telegraph. After more than 180 years of constant growth and innovation, we are living in the age of information. Vast data networks span our connected world – but to design them effectively humans need tools more sophisticated than the engineer's “gut feeling”. To solve large-scale, highly-constrained problems we turn to our best teacher – nature. It is expected that nature-inspired methods and other metaheuristics will play an important role in solving the big optimization challenges of real-life telecommunication industry problems.

References

1. Garey, M.R. and D.S. Johnson, *Computers and Intractability; A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness*. Bell Telephone Laboratories, Inc.(1979)
2. J. e. a. Dreco, *Metaheuristics for Hard Optimization*, Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg (2006).
3. M. Gendrau, "An Introduction to Tabu Search," in *Handbook of Metaheuristics*, Kluwer Academic Publishers (2002).
4. N. Sabri, M. Puteh and M. Mahmood, "An overview of Gravitational Search Algorithm utilization in optimization problems," in *IEEE 3rd International Conference on System Engineering and Technology*, (2013).
5. P. Rabanal, I. Rodrigues and F. Rubio, "Using River Formation Dynamics to Design Heuristic Algorithms," in *International Conference on Unconventional Computation (in LNCS vol 4618)*, (2007).
6. X.-S. Yang, "Harmony Search as a Metaheuristic Algorithm," *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol. 191, (2009).
7. R. Rurenbar, "Simulated annealing algorithms: an overview," *IEEE Circuits and Devices Magazine*, vol. 5, no. 1, (1989).
8. Z. Michalewicz, *Genetic Algorithms + Data Structures = Evolution Programs*, Springer, (1996).
9. M. Dorigo, V. Maniezzo and A. Colomi, "Ant System: Optimization by a Colony of Cooperating Agents," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, vol. 26, no. 1, (1996).
10. D. Karaboga and B. B., "Artificial bee colony optimization algorithm for solving constrained optimization problems," *LNCS*, vol. 4529, Springer, Heidelberg (2007).
11. X. Yang and X. He, "Firefly Algorithm: Recent Advances and Applications," *Int. J. Swarm Intelligence*, vol. 1, no. 1, (2013).
12. IHS Markit, "The Internet of Things: a movement, not a market," https://cdn.ihs.com/www/pdf/IoT_ebook.pdf, last accessed 2020/12/9.
13. World Economic Forum, "What happens in an internet minute in 2017?," [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/08/what-happens-in-an-internet-minute-in-2017>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
14. Ericsson, "Mobile subscriptions outlook", <https://www.ericsson.com/en/mobility-report/reports/june-2020/mobile-subscriptions-outlook>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
15. Cisco, "Cisco Visual Networking Index: Global Mobile Data Traffic Forecast Update, 2016–2021 White Paper", <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/service-provider/visual-networking-index-vni/mobile-white-paper-cl11-520862.html>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
16. IUT, <https://www.itu.int/en/mediacentre/Pages/2018-PR40.aspx>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
17. E. Alba and J. F. Chicano, "Evolutionary algorithms in telecommunications," *MELECON 2006 - 2006 IEEE Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference*, Malaga, (2006)
18. National Air and Space Administration, "LADEE mission page" https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/ladee/main/index.html, 2014, last accessed 2020/12/9.
19. "National Space Sciences Data Center - Ranger 7," National Air and Space Administration, <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraftDisplay.do?id=1964-041A>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
20. E. Michielssen, J. Sajer, S. Ranjithan and R. Mittra, "Design of Lightweight, Broad-band Microwave Absorbers Using Genetic Algorithms," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory & Techniques*, vol. 41, no. 6, (1993).
21. National Air and Space Administration, "Space Technology 5," (2006).

22. G. Hornby, A. Globus, D. Linden and J. Lohn, "Automated Antenna Design with Evolutionary Algorithms," in Space 2006, AIAA Space Forum, San Jose, California, (2006).
23. J. Lohn, D. Linden, B. Belvins, T. Greenling and M. Allard, "Automated Synthesis of a Lunar Satellite Antenna System," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 63, no. 4, (2015).
24. F. Villegas, "Parallel Genetic-Algorithm Optimization of Shaped Beam Coverage Areas Using Planar 2-D Phased Arrays," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 55, no. 6, (2007).
25. M. Randall, A. Levis, A. Galehdar and D. Thiel, "Using Ant Colony Optimisation to Improve the Efficiency of Small Meander Line RFID Antennas," in 3rd IEEE International Conference on e-Science and Grid Computing, (2007).
26. F. Mohamadi Monavar, N. Komjani and P. Mousavi, "Application of Invasive Weed Optimization to Design a Broadband Patch Antenna With Symmetric Radiation Pattern," IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, vol. 10, (2011).
27. K. Abdul Rani and F. Malek, "Symmetric linear antenna array geometry synthesis using cuckoo search metaheuristic algorithm," in The 17th Asia Pacific Conference on Communications, (2011).
28. R. Bera, D. Mandal, S. Ghoshal and R. Kar, "Optimal design of concentric elliptical array antenna for maximum side-lobe level reduction using particle swarm optimization with aging leader and challengers," in International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing, (2016).
29. J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "Particle Swarm Optimization," in Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Neural Networks, (1995).
30. D. Linden, "A system for evolving antennas in-situ," in Proceedings Third NASA/DoD Workshop on Evolvable Hardware, (2001).
31. J. Infantolino, M. Barney and R. Haupt, "Optimal Position for an Antenna using a Genetic Algorithm," in Applied Computational Electromagnetics Society Conference ACES 2010, (2010).
32. P. Sindhuja, Y. Kuwahara, K. Kumaki and Y. Hiramatsu, "A Design of Vehicular GPS and LTE Antenna Considering the Vehicular Body Effects," Progress In Electromagnetics Research, pp. 75-87, (2014).
33. C. Lee, "Maximizing Read Accuracy by Using Genetic Algorithms to Locate RFID Reader Antennas at the Portals," Journal of Software, vol. 5, (2010).
34. S. Liao, C. Chen, C. Chiu, M. Ho and T. W. B. Wysocki, "Optimal receiver antenna location in indoor environment using dynamic differential evolution and genetic algorithm," EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking, no. 235, (2013).
35. Y. Yang, Y. Wu, M. Xia and Z. Qin, "A RFID Network Planning Method Based on Genetic Algorithm," in Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Networks Security, Wireless Communication and Trusted Computing, Vol. 1, (2009).
36. T. Garcia-Valverde, A. Garcia-Sola, J. Botia and A. Gomes-Skarmeta, "Automatic Design of an Indoor User Location Infrastructure Using a Memetic Multiobjective Approach," IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, vol. 42, no. 5, (2012).
37. K. Pickert, "Invisible Wires," New York Magazine, 04 10 2004, <https://nymag.com/ny-metro/news/people/columns/intelligencer/9957/>, last accessed 2020/12/9.
38. F. Rofii, M. Toscani and D. Siswanto, "Optimization of coverage and the number of base transceiver station towers using fuzzy C-Means and genetic algorithm," Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, vol. 93, no. 1, (2016).

39. J. Munyaneza, A. Kurien and B. Van Wyk, "Optimization of Antenna Placement in 3G Networks using Genetic Algorithm," in 3rd International Conference on Broadband Communications, Information Technology & Biomedical Applications, (2008).
40. S. Lee, S. Lee, K. Kim, D. Griffith and N. Golmie, "Optimal Deployment of Pico Base Stations in LTE-A Heterogeneous Networks," *Computer Networks*, vol. 72, (2014).
41. H. Ghazzai, E. Yaacoub and M. Alouini, "Optimized LTE Cell Planning With Varying Spatial and Temporal User Densities," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 65, no. 3, (2016).
42. M. Komala, I. Wahidah and Isikmal, "LTE Networks BTS Location Optimization with Double Step Grey Wolf Optimizer," in 11th International Conference on Telecommunication Systems Services and Applications (TSSA), (2017).
43. S. Cahon, E. Talbi and N. Melab, "A parallel and hybrid Multi-Objective Evolutionary algorithm applied to the design of cellular networks," in IEEE Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference, (2006).
44. S. Parija and P. Sahu, "A Metaheuristic Bat Inspired Technique for Cellular Network Optimization," in 2nd International Conference on Man and Machine Interfacing, (2017).
45. X. Yang, "A New Metaheuristic Bat-Inspired Algorithm," *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol. 284, (2010).
46. S. Mendes, G. Molina, M. Vega-Rodriguez, Y. Gomez-Pulido, G. Miranda, C. Segura, E. Alba, P. Isasi, C. Leon and J. Sanchez-Perez, "Benchmarking a Wide Spectrum of Metaheuristic Techniques for the Radio Network Design Problem," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 13, no. 5, (2009).
47. L. Hu, I. Kovacs, P. Mogensen, O. Klein and W. Stomer, "Optimal New Site Deployment Algorithm for Heterogeneous Cellular Networks," in IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC Fall), (2011).
48. S. Salcedo-Sanz, J. Del Ser, I. Landa-Torres, S. Gil-López and J. Portilla-Figueras, "The Coral Reefs Optimization Algorithm: A Novel Metaheuristic for Efficiently Solving Optimization Problems," *The Scientific World Journal*, (2014).
49. S. Salcedo-Sanz, J. P.-F. A. Sanchez-Garcia, S. Jimenez-Fernandez and A. Ahmadzadeh, "A coral-reef optimization algorithm for the optimal service distribution problem in mobile radio access networks," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 25, no. 11, (2014).
50. D. Tse and P. Viswanath, "Fundamentals of Wireless Communication", Cambridge University Press, (2005).
51. A. F. Molisch and M. Z. Win, "MIMO systems with antenna selection," *IEEE Micro*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 46–56, Mar.–Apr. (2004).
52. P. D. Karamalis, N. D. Skentos and A. G. Kanatas, "Selecting array configurations for MIMO systems: an evolutionary computation approach," in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 1994–1998, Nov. (2004).
53. H.-Y. Lu and W.-H. Fang, "Joint transmit/receive antenna selection in MIMO systems based on the priority-based genetic algorithm," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Lett.*, vol. 6, pp. 588–591, (2007).
54. J. Lain, "Joint Transmit/Receive Antenna Selection for MIMO Systems: A Real-Valued Genetic Approach," in *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 58–60, January (2011).
55. A. Gorokhov, D. Gore, and A. Paulraj, "Performance bounds for antenna selection in MIMO systems," in *IEEE Proc. Int. Conf. Communications*, May 11–15, (2003).
56. Z. Abdullah, C. C. Tsimenidis and M. Johnston, "Tabu search vs. bio-inspired algorithms for antenna selection in spatially correlated massive MIMO uplink channels," 2016 24th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO), Budapest, (2016).

57. K. C. Fountoukidis, K. Siakavara, S. K. Goudos and C. Kallalakis, "Antenna selection for MIMO systems using biogeography based optimization," 2017 International Workshop on Antenna Technology: Small Antennas, Innovative Structures, and Applications (iWAT), Athens, (2017).
58. D. Simon, "Biogeography-Based Optimization," IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, vol. 12, pp. 702-713, (2008).
59. N. Sindhwani, M. S. Bhamrah, A. Garg and D. Kumar, "Performance analysis of particle swarm optimization and genetic algorithm in MIMO systems," 2017 8th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), Delhi, (2017).
60. A. B. Gershman, N. D. Sidiropoulos, S. Shahbazpanahi, M. Bengtsson and B. Ottersten, "Convex optimization-based beamforming," IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 62–75, (2010).
61. Y. F. Liu, Y. H. Dai, and Z. Q. Luo, "Coordinated beamforming for misinterference channel: Complexity analysis and efficient algorithms," IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 1142–1157, (2011).
62. X. Gao, L. Dai, C. Yuen, and Z. Wang, "Turbo-like beamforming based on Tabu search algorithm for millimeter-wave massive MIMO systems", IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol., vol. 65, no. 7, pp. 5731–5737, (2016).
63. L. Du, L. Li and Y. Xu, "A genetic antenna selection algorithm with heuristic beamforming for massive MIMO systems," 2016 19th International Symposium on Wireless Personal Multimedia Communications (WPMC), Shenzhen, (2016).
64. P. Bento, C. H. Antunes, M. Gomes, R. Dinis and V. Silva, "Beamforming Optimization for Multiuser Wireless Systems Using Meta-Heuristics," 2016 IEEE 84th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC-Fall), Montreal, QC, (2016).
65. Chiu, C.-C., Lai, G.-D. & Cheng, Y.-T"Self-adaptive dynamic differential evolution applied to BER reduction with beamforming techniques for ultra wideband MU-MIMO systems". Prog. Electromag. Res. 87: 187-197, (2018).
66. C. Doroody, T. S. Kiong and S. Darzi, "SINR improvement using Firefly Algorithm (FA) for Linear Constrained Minimum Variance (LCMV) beamforming technique," 2015 International Conference on Computer, Communications, and Control Technology (I4CT), Kuching, (2015).
67. S. Darzi, T. S. Kiong, and M. Aghaei, "Overview of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) for Smart Antenna Beamforming," in Proceedings National Graduate Conference, Tenaga, (2012).
68. S. N. Shahab, A. R. Zainun, N. H. Noordin, I. I. Mohamed and W. D. Abdullah, "Null steering Optimization based MVDR beamformer using hybrid PSOGSA approach for antenna array system," 2016 IEEE Student Conference on Research and Development (SCORED), Kuala Lumpur, (2016).
69. H. Ochiai, P. Mitran, H. V. Poor and V. Tarokh, "Collaborative beamforming for distributed wireless ad hoc sensor networks," in IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 53, no. 11, pp. 4110-4124, (2005).
70. S. Jayaprakasam, S. K. B. A. Rahim, and C. Y. Leow, "A Pareto Elite Selection Genetic Algorithm for Random Antenna Array Beamforming with Low Sidelobe Level," Progress In Electromagnetics Research B, Vol. 51, 407-425, (2013).
71. S. Jayaprakasam, S. K. Abdul Rahim, C. Y. Leow and M. F. Mohd Yusof, "Beampattern optimization in distributed beamforming using multiobjective and metaheuristic method," 2014 IEEE Symposium on Wireless Technology and Applications (ISWTA), Kota Kinabalu, (2014).